

S E A R C H F O R N E W A M O E B A C I D E S . P A R T I I

BY C. N. KACHRU AND B. PATEAK

Synthesis of α -(2-alkyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamines having substitution of methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl and *n*-hexyl has been made by the reduction of the appropriate 2-alkyl-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone oxime with sodium and absolute alcohol.

In Part I (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 611) we have described the synthesis of some β -(2-alkyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamines which are the outcomes of hypothetical opening in the emetine molecule at certain points. If the opening in the emetine molecule (I) is considered at other points, shown by the dotted lines 'b', a portion of the molecule transforms to the type of compound (II). It has been considered desirable to synthesise such compounds having methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl and *n*-hexyl groups for R, so that they may be tested for amoebacidal activity,

These compounds have been synthesised by the route shown below.

Acetomethylveratrone (B; R=Me) was prepared by Harding and Weizmann (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1127) and by Fargher and Parkin (*ibid.*, 1921, 119, 1724) by condensing methylveratrole with acetyl chloride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride in good yield. Following the procedure higher members of 2-alkyl-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone (B) have been prepared, though not in good yields. It has been found that major portion of the condensation product appears as a demethylated product. Methylation has been effected with dimethyl sulphate. Oximes (C) of these ketones on reduction with sodium in absolute alcohol in the usual manner have resulted in good yields of the desired amines (II).

* E X P E R I M E N T A L

α -(2-Methyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine (II).—2-methyl-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone oxime (Fargher and Parkin, *loc. cit.*, 10 g.) was dissolved in dry alcohol and

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected.

was reduced with metallic sodium (15 g.). The mass was cooled, acidified with HCl (conc.), alcohol was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the residual solid was dissolved in water. Any unchanged mass was removed by extraction with benzene. The aqueous layer was then made alkaline with NaOH solution and the separated amine was extracted with ether. Ethereal extract was dried over KOH and the amine was distilled in vacuum, b.p. $158^{\circ}\text{-}60^{\circ}/5\text{mm}$, yield 4 g. (43%). The *picrate* was crystallised from alcohol as brown needles, m.p. 250° (decomp.). Its *hydrochloride* crystallised from ethyl acetate in colorless needles, m.p. $190\text{-}92^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 56.6; H, 7.7; N, 6.3. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$ requires C, 57.0; H, 7.7; N, 6.1%.)

2-Ethyl-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone (B: R=Et).—A mixture of ethylveratrole (A: R=Et) (42 g.), acetyl chloride (27 g.) and dry CS_2 (150 c.c.) was thoroughly cooled in an ice-bath. To this mixture AlCl_3 (anhyd., 84 g.) was added in portions with thorough shaking, and the mixture was kept at 0° for 7 hours. It was then warmed on a water-bath for half an hour. CS_2 was removed by distillation and the residual mass was decomposed by ice and water. The ketone was recovered in the usual manner. A portion underwent demethylation and it was remethylated with dimethyl sulphate. The ketone boiled at $140^{\circ}/2\text{ mm}$ and solidified on cooling. It crystallised from alcohol in colorless prisms, m.p. 58° , yield 23 g. (43.7%). (Found: C, 69.35; H, 7.7. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 69.2; H, 7.7%.)

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from alcohol in brown needles, m.p. $176\text{-}77^{\circ}$. The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. $182\text{-}83^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 15.7. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires N, 15.8%.)

2-Ethyl-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone Oxime (C: R=Et).—A mixture of 2-ethyl-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone (13 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (13 g.), sodium acetate (26 g.) and water (25 c.c.) was dissolved in minimum amount of alcohol by heating and refluxed for one hour. On diluting with water, the oxime separated out as white needles. It crystallised from hot water in colorless needles, m.p. $95\text{-}96^{\circ}$, yield 12 g. (Found: N, 6.4. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 6.3%.)

α -(2-Ethyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine (II: R=Et).—The above oxime was reduced with metallic sodium in absolute alcohol in a manner described before. The amine boiled at $140\text{-}42^{\circ}/3\text{mm}$, yield 38.8%. The *picrate* crystallised from alcohol as brown needles, m.p. 255° (decomp.). The *hydrochloride* crystallised from 100% alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. $193\text{-}94^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 58.3; H, 8.2; N, 5.9. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$ requires C, 58.7; H, 8.1; N, 5.7%.)

2-n-Propyl-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone (B: R = n-Pr).—*n*-Propyl-3:4-dimethoxybenzene (A: R = n-Pr; 20 g.) was allowed to react with acetyl chloride (15 g.) in CS_2 (100 c.c.) at ice-cold temperature with the gradual addition of AlCl_3 (anhyd., 40 g.) in a manner described before. The ketone boiled at $158^{\circ}/4\text{ mm}$, yield 13 g. (52%). It was a viscous liquid and did not solidify. The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 102. (Found: N, 15.2. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 15.0%.)

2-n-Propyl-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone Oxime (C: R = n-Pr).—The oxime was prepared in a manner as described before. On crystallisation from dilute alcohol it appeared as colorless short prisms, m.p. 82° . (Found: N, 5.0. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 5.9%.)

α -(2-*n*-Propyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine (II: R = *n* Pr).—2-*n*-Propyl-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone oxime was reduced by metallic sodium in dry alcohol, as described before. The amine boiled at 160°/4 mm, yield 57%. The *picrate* crystallised from hot water as brown needles, m.p. 211°. The *hydrochloride* crystallised in colorless needles from absolute alcohol, m.p. 206°. (Found: N, 5.5; OMe, 23.9. C₁₃H₂₃O₂NCl requires N, 5.4; OMe, 23.9%).

2-*n*-Butyl-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone (B: R = *n*-Bu).—1-*n*-Butyl-4:5-dimethoxybenzene (A: R = *n*-Bu; 20 g.) was allowed to react with acetyl chloride (8.5 g.) in dry CS₂ (100 c.c.) at ice-cold temperature with the gradual addition of AlCl₃ (anhyd., 40 g.). The ketone was recovered subsequently in the usual manner. The ketone boiled at 175°/4 mm, yield 13.5 g. (55%). It did not solidify. (Found: C, 70.7; H, 8.8. C₁₄H₂₀O₂ requires C, 71.2; H, 8.4%).

α -(2-Butyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine (II: R = *n*-Bu).—The oxime of the above ketone (B: R = *n*-Bu) was prepared in the usual manner. The crude oxime was a viscous liquid and it was reduced with sodium and absolute alcohol. The amine distilled at 160-62°/3 mm, yield 42% of the theoretical.

The *picrate* crystallised from hot water as brown needles. It changed colour at 200° and melted at 240° with decomposition. The *hydrochloride* crystallised in colorless needles from absolute alcohol, m.p. 165-66°. (Found: C, 61.1, H, 8.9; N, 5.2. C₁₄H₂₄O₂NCl requires C, 61.5; H, 8.8; N, 5.1%).

2-*n*-Hexyl-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone (B: R = *n*-Hex).—1-*n*-Hexyl-4:5-dimethoxybenzene (A: R = *n*-Hex; 20 g.) was allowed to react with acetyl chloride (10 g.) in dry CS₂ (100 c.c.) at ice-cold temperature with the gradual addition of AlCl₃ (anhyd., 30 g.). The ketone distilled at 162-65°/2 mm, yield 6 g. (25% of theoretical). (Found: C, 72.1; H, 9.4. C₁₆H₂₄O₂ requires C, 72.7; H, 9.1%).

α -(2-*n*-Hexyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine (II: R = *n*-Hex).—The oxime of the above ketone (B: R = *n*-Hex), prepared in the usual manner, was obtained as a viscous liquid. The crude oxime was reduced with sodium and absolute alcohol. After the reduction was over, the mass was acidified with HCl and the alcohol removed under reduced pressure. The residual mass on treatment with water left an insoluble solid which was filtered and washed with cold water. It was found to be the amine hydrochloride which was purified by crystallisation from hot water in colorless needles, m.p. 178°, yield 58% of the theoretical. (Found: C, 63.6; H, 9.5; N, 4.3. C₁₆H₂₈O₂NCl requires C, 63.7; H, 9.3; N, 4.6%). The *picrate* crystallised from alcohol as brown needles, m.p. 177-78°.

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